

Listen to the Earth Speaking to Us

Linette Lobo

St. Vincent's Jr College, Pune

Isiah 26: 20- Go, my people, enter your rooms and shut the doors behind you; hide yourselves for a little while until His wrath has passed by.

This time of coronavirus, though a time of terrible test and trial, leaves us with many lessons to learn. It Tests our faith in the Lord, our patience with our loved ones, our sensitivity towards our neighbours by not hoarding things and our love for all mankind by staying indoors.

Although COVID-19 has disrupted our daily life, our work, our schedule, it is undeniable and unavoidable the benefits it is doing to nature – our ozone layer is improving, our pollution levels are dropping and we have all realised how dispensable we all are. How the world will still go on without humans, better in fact!

Crying Out for Help

In such times of crisis we turn and return to God, we cry out for help, and sometimes we start doubting if God really listens, if he really exists, and if he does, why does he put his people through the test?

We all believe that our life is a gift from God and we pray to him that we may join him in life eternal after we pass from this world. Then why do we fear death?

Psalm 112:7 They will have no fear of bad news; their hearts are steadfast, trusting in the Lord

Psalm 31:24 Be strong and take heart, all you who hope in the LORD.

Pope Francis recently addressed the people and asked them to keep faith, be strong and believe in the Lord narrating a passage from the Bible. But how many of us actually can freely surrender our lives in the hands of God and say that “Lord I place my life into your hands. Let your will be done”? How many can really resolve to say? “In these trying times that I have on this earth let me be good, let me be helpful and let me reach out to someone.” Especially in these difficult times, we can reach out to the people who need our help, to the sick, the suffering and the old.

Corinthians 1:10 - I appeal to you brothers and sisters in the name of our Lord Jesus Christ that all of you agree with one another in what you say and that there be no divisions among you but that you be perfectly united in mind and thought.

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Overcoming the Evil by the Good

Jesus saved us by taking upon himself all the suffering and humiliation, without complaining but with humility, grace, courage and obedience, purely out of love. God did not take away the evil that crushed Jesus in his suffering but rather strengthened him so that our evil could be overcome by good and love that loves to the very end. We need to keep in mind especially in these times of crisis, when we feel alone, abandoned and at a dead end, with no hope or way out, when we doubt the presence of God and feel that he is not responding to our prayers, we must remember that we are not alone, Jesus

too experienced all that we go through and more and yet he kept faith in His father, and surrendered totally to him. “Father if possible, take this cup from me; however not my will but your will be done.”

The Lord knows our hearts better than we do, he knows how weak and faltering we are, how many times we fall and how hard it is for us to rise up again after our fall and how difficult it is to heal certain wounds. And that is why he promises us, ‘I will heal them through their faithlessness, I will love them deeply’.

In spite of the trauma, I think that we may be able to draw blessing even from this dreaded corona experience. It calls us to focus on what’s really important, it shows us that we don’t need much to survive, just the essentials!

It reminds us that we have come alone and we will be going back alone and this life what we are given is not a rat race, but it is a gift, a precious gift. It takes us back to our roots, to keep life simple and uncomplicated and cut out all the negative noise and situations that we put ourselves into.

It’s a time to rediscover ourselves, to realise that life is not worth living without love and service to others, to go deeper into your own selves. And if we all survive this covid-19 period. We have a chance to start our lives afresh and anew. Leaving all that is unnecessary and negative behind, we can learn to be resurrected people in Christ, Easter people.

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97

As Easter people, we are called take root in the ground, live in harmony with the wind, plant your seeds in the winter, and rejoice with the birds of the coming of spring. Life is simple. We just need to be aware of what’s important and lasting. We can be a blessing to so many around us, in spite of these terrible, trying times!

98